

EBFMC25-OP-25 · Time to Start Rotations in Family Medicine Residency Program: A Training and Research Hospital Experience

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: In Turkey, the duration of family medicine residency training, as approved by the Board of Medical Specialization, is 36 months. Of this period, 18 months are allocated to clinical rotations in designated medical disciplines, with the specific branches and durations clearly defined. However, the precise sequence in which these rotations are to be undertaken has not been explicitly established.

This study aimed to evaluate the timing of the initiation of clinical rotations within the family medicine residency training program conducted at a training and research hospital.

Material and Methods: For this study, the start dates of residency training and the mandatory rotation start dates between January 2018 and the end of February 2025 for residents who have completed or are currently undergoing their residency training at Trabzon Kanuni Training and Research Hospital were obtained from institutional records. For those who started their residency training within the first 15 days of the month, that month was considered as the 1st month; for those who started within the second half of the month, the following month was accepted as the 1st month. The nine rotations and their durations specified in version 2.4 of the Family Medicine Residency Core Curriculum (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2018) were taken as the basis.

Results: The number of residents whose data were evaluated in the study was 64. Accordingly, 364 out of a total of 576 rotations (%69.2) were accessed. The start times of the rotations were as follows: Emergency Medicine at the 9.52nd month (n=51), Internal Medicine at the 11.2nd month (n=45), Cardiology at the 12.42nd month (n=52), General Surgery at the 12.48th month (n=41), Obstetrics and Gynecology at the 15th month (n=37), Pediatrics at the 16.2nd month (n=47), Pulmonology at the 20.9th month (n=33), Psychiatry at the 22.5th month (n=30), and Dermatology and Venereal Diseases at the 23.8th month (n=28). The rotations started within the first year were as follows: Emergency Medicine 80.3% (n=41), General Surgery 61% (n=25), Internal Medicine 60% (n=27), Cardiology 53.8% (n=28), Obstetrics and Gynecology 40.5% (n=15), Pediatrics 34% (n=16), Pulmonology 18.1% (n=6), Psychiatry 10% (n=3), and Dermatology and Venereal Diseases 3.5% (n=1).

Conclusion: This study reveals that the start times of rotations in family medicine residency training show significant variability, with rotations such as Internal Medicine and Emergency Medicine concentrated in the early years of the residency, while specialties like Dermatology and Venereal Diseases are postponed to the later stages of the training.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Family medicine residency, clinical rotation, time factors.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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